

POTENTIAL FOR INTERACTION BETWEEN SCHOOL AND UNIVERSITY

¹O.V. Savenko, ²E.E. Jumayev, ³B.I. Abraykulov

¹Assistant at Termez State University

²Associate Professor Termez Institute of Agricultural Technologies and Innovative Development

³Director of vocational school No. 2 of Shurchi district of Surkhandarya region

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to determining the potential for interaction between innovative schools and a classical university to improve the quality of education. When determining potential, the methodology of humanitarian research of innovation is used, an empirical analysis of precedents of the phenomenon being studied is essential for such a methodology, which allows not only to identify the potential of interaction, build its empirical models, but also to characterize the features of the potential in different models.*

Keywords: *interaction; potential; innovative schools; university; empirical models.*

In recent years, interaction between universities and schools has become not only an area of educational management, but also a subject of research attention. It is noted that traditional and stable connections between universities and schools as separate stages (levels) of the education system are undergoing significant changes. On the one hand, this allows us to demonstrate the peculiarities of the existing practice of interaction, and on the other hand, to characterize the directions for improving its quality.

The difficulties of studying the interaction between universities and schools lie in the fact that the current practice is presented as “natural” relations between different levels of one education system. And, as is usually the case with what is “natural” and “determined,” the interaction between university and school does not become the subject of reflection and criticism.

The intensity of the process of reforming the education system, the totality of the change in the system, expressed in the change of everyone, every step and level, revealed both the features of the current state of this interaction and the potential that it has.

It was discovered that the established practice of interaction between different levels of education is determined by hierarchical connections and relationships (higher school “dictates” to the secondary school its ideas about the quality of students’ training, and this “quality” is equal to admission to a university); expansion of educational tasks solved in higher education to the “lower” level of education (reduction of the tasks of general education to prepare children for entering a university); the spread and totalization of the “university” method of education at the senior level of secondary school.

In the modern world, the role of education is obvious. Education is one of the most important conditions for the development of the economy and civil society. Significant changes in the socio-economic structure of Uzbekistan are affecting the school, which is forced and must change in order to meet the requirements of the state and society.

Integration is the unification of objects or parts according to some characteristic in order to obtain an interconnected system. Education is a very complex system; it has many components that must be interconnected. Of course, there are no ideal systems either in nature or in society. The ideal is unattainable, so there is always something to strive for, and even more so in education.

Any system works effectively only in the presence of feedback, when one link improves, adapting to the requirements of another. Therefore, the school and the university must learn to hear each other and develop forms of cooperation that will solve two main problems:

- Increasing the level of knowledge of graduates – future applicants;
- Information and career guidance activities aimed at making graduates' conscious choice of specialty and increasing motivation to study.

The main directions of interaction between universities and schools at the present stage:

- Educational and methodological interaction, which includes the preparation and testing of textbooks, educational and methodological aids for students and teachers working in schools; management of educational activities in specialized disciplines; contacts between school teachers and university professors for the purpose of consultation and exchange of experience.

– Scientific and methodological work, which contains the following forms: holding joint round tables on the most important issues of joint activities, organizing methodological seminars at university departments with the participation of school teachers; organization of annual student scientific and practical conferences with the involvement of school students; peer review by university teachers of research and design works of school students; attracting school teachers to participate in scientific and practical conferences at the university; holding subject Olympiads and competitions among secondary school students at the university; organization of electives and scientific clubs on the basis of universities, aimed at school students; provision of methodological assistance to university teachers in the development of curricula for secondary educational institutions in specialized disciplines; preparation and publication of joint scientific collections of articles, textbooks, monographs summarizing the work experience of teachers and methodologists, based on the results of scientific research, organizing research activities for high school students under the guidance of university teachers, providing a university base for improving the knowledge of school students (the opportunity to use the resources of the university's scientific library), involving university teachers in preparing schoolchildren for regional and republican olympiads and competitions.

In turn, the school is a platform for scientific research. The school is a laboratory, a base of practice, providing a huge testing ground for scientific research. There is a lot of "raw" material here that can be used as the basis for a candidate's or doctoral research. University specialists have the opportunity to conduct a high-quality examination of the rich information base that the school has developed over many years. First of all, this concerns pedagogical methodology. Therefore, there is an urgent need for serious examination, assessment, and audit using the resources of higher education. The school is also a practice base for acquiring and improving the methodological skills of students receiving a teacher's diploma. This is where students can test the competencies acquired at the university. But the internal potential of schools for renewal is being exhausted for both objective and subjective reasons. Therefore, interaction with universities today is not a desire of individual schools, but a necessity for the entire general education system. And it's not for nothing that the most successful schools are those that have long established strong ties with universities. Termez is a typical medium-sized city in Uzbekistan. The educational dominant of the city is the Termez Institute of Agricultural Technologies and Innovative Development. Many city school graduates choose it to continue their education. The Termez Institute of Agricultural Technologies and Innovative Development is a center of attraction for applicants from many regions of the neighboring Kashkadarya region. The positive side of the Termez Institute of Agricultural

Technologies and Innovative Development is that its results can be accepted as entrance exams by most universities in the country.

Therefore, the Termez Institute of Agricultural Technologies and Innovative Development is working to enhance interaction with schools in the city of Shurchi. Many of the forms of work listed above have already become traditional; the institute has only just begun to develop some areas. In addition to traditional career guidance work, holding an Open Day, this is the involvement of departments in working with schoolchildren, the involvement of students and school teachers to participate in scientific and practical conferences, the organization of advanced training courses for teachers in accordance with the needs of the city's teaching community.

The "School-University" interaction program is being implemented in vocational school No. 2 of the Shurchinsky district of the Surkhandarya region. University teachers are involved in the educational process, provide consulting assistance to teachers, and assist in the development of curricula for secondary educational institutions for elective courses.

The participation of schoolchildren in annual student scientific and practical conferences at the Termez Institute of Agricultural Technologies and Innovative Development is being revived, teachers publish their articles in institute collections of scientific works. A survey of school teachers showed a high level of awareness of the essence and importance of integration between schools and universities. The majority of school teachers surveyed note that the interaction between higher and secondary schools expands the overall educational space and improves the quality of education, and all subjects included in this interaction benefit.

The university gets a real idea of the level of training of modern schoolchildren and the opportunity to participate in its improvement, receiving well-prepared applicants and students.

In turn, the school is interested in growing its prestige and status in the education market. Teachers can improve their professional skills by supplementing it with new forms of activity and new types of knowledge. Students will receive an education that meets modern requirements and standards, as well as research skills. Parents have the opportunity to learn about the requirements for education at a university, as well as make sure that their children are making the right professional choice.

Thus, the system of cooperation between schools and universities, even in a small city, can currently be built in such a way as to maximally satisfy the diverse needs of students, provide the opportunity to obtain higher education in various fields, which will provide graduates with promising and interesting work in the future, competitiveness and demand in the labor market.

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